

An integrated expert-based methodological framework to map badlands in different morpho-climatic contexts: preliminary results

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Badlands are among the most complex soil and sediment erosion landforms and are widespread worldwide across different morpho-climatic contexts. In recent decades, several authors have mapped badlands based on field surveys, stereo-orthophotos, Google Earth imagery, topographic land surface models and other remote sensing data acquired

from various platforms. The mapping approach is usually chosen based on a combination of badland occurrence and with the availability of data in specific study areas.

Different mapping methods were implemented by considering the entire badlands watershed, the badlands' erosion landform (including or excluding the vegetation growing inside badlands) and finally considering or not the badland's sub-watershed.

The mapping approach is the base on which further studies on landforms (e.g., susceptibility models, geomorphological dynamics etc.) are carried out. Thus, significant differences in mapping methods may lead to considerable variations in the model outputs.

The work here proposed aims to introduce an expert-based method to map badlands in different morpho-climatic contexts in a standardized way. The methodology was tested in a representative area close to Montalbano Jonico (MT), Basilicata Region, Southern Italy. In this area, the stratigraphic interval represented by the Ideal Section (IS) has been recently designated as a Standard Auxiliary Boundary Strato-type (SABS) for the Global Boundary Stratotype Section and Point (GSSP) of the Middle Pleistocene Subseries/Subepoch and Chibanian Stage/Age at the Chiba section, Japan.

The expert-based methodology was developed in collaboration with the IAG Badlands Working Group and aims to address the following questions: i) Is it possible to univocally map the badland surface in different morpho-climatic contexts in a globally consistent way? ii) Can a landform database be defined that contains basic morphological, lithological and morphometric features that allow homogenisation of the data associated with each mapped landform?

Three different badland types were defined based on mapping scale and morphological characteristics: i) Isolated Badlands, ii) Badland Surfaces, iii) Badland Landscapes. In addition, a specific geodatabase was associated with each mapped landform, implementing geological, climatic, and morphometrical attributes to obtain a useful database for each landform. The proposed methodology aims to standardize the mapping approach by defining cartographic and geomorphological rules that could allow for creating a homogeneous badlands inventory map at a global scale.

KEYWORDS: badlands, geodatabase, inventory map, mapping

Assessment of pseudo-badlands forms and features through multi scale-multi sensor geomorphological approach in alpine context: the 'Becca d'Aver DsGSD' case study, Aosta Valley, (Italy)

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The aim of this work is to characterize the pseudo-badlands morphology associated with deeply altered bedrock materials in a deep-seated gravitational slope deformation context through an integrated geomorphological approach. The area covers approximately 11.5 km² representing the Cretaz-Comba Basset basin, a portion of slope on the left side of the Aosta Valley, Northern Italy. The study area is characterized by several gravitational and runoff associated processes that interact with villages and anthropogenic structures. Moreover, semi-consolidated scree slope, glacial deposits as well as muck deposits mantle the area supplying sediments that can be eroded and transported as debris flow. However, pseudo-badlands landforms represent the main source of sediments providing loose materials highly connected with the main drainage system. The outlet of the basin reaches the village of Champagne built on an active fan. For this reason, a detailed geomorphological characterization of active landforms is essential to understand the potential geo-hydrological risk in the area.

The pseudo-badlands forms and features were mapped through field survey, Google Earth, remote sensing interpretation. In addition, a detailed geomorphological map was realized applying the MorphDB (Bosino et al., GFDQ). Furthermore, the geological strength index (GSI) was applied to evaluate discontinuity conditions of the rocks cropping out in the pseudo badlands systems.

Finally, dedicated terrain analysis, connectivity index model and remotely sensed data were applied to highlight the contribution of pseudo-badlands in sediment transport. In particular either radar and optical remote sensing data were implemented to support the mapping operations. On one hand, InSAR data, also through post processing tools such as Principal Component Analysis, were used to identify active sectors, on the other hand, optical multi- and hyper-spectral imagery was introduced to detect bare soil areas precisely.

The results of this study highlight how altered bedrock materials, as well as anthropogenic muck deposits can contribute to provide sediments that are related to hydrogeological risk in the area.

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KEYWORDS: pseudo badlands erosion, geomorphological mapping, hyperspectral analysis, connectivity index, WebGIS
